

Automated modelling of residential buildings and heating systems based on smart grid monitoring data

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ABSTRACT

More than 60% of the energy is consumed in European households for space heating. Combined with the currently low renovation rate, the realization of the 2000 W society will be challenging. A fast and remote detection of optimal retrofit targets may help to address this problem. In this contribution, a novel procedure to characterise a building and its heating systems from smart grid monitoring data is presented. The parameters of a simplified physical simulation model for the building and heating system are adjusted to match the simulated and the actual power consumption of the heat pump. The method is validated on three reference buildings with almost perfect reproduction of the heat consumption over the course of one year and good recovery of relevant building/heating system parameters. The application on five real-world buildings shows the possibility to reproduce the annual heat consumption within a maximal deviation of 5% in four out of five cases. These convincing results enable also the application of the developed procedure as a load prediction tool.

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1. Introduction

Almost two thirds of the residential energy demand [1] is spent on space heating and cooling. Therefore, a key aspect for the decarbonisation of the energy selector is the increase of the heating system's efficiency as well as a large-scale analysis of the building properties. On the other hand, more and more European countries roll-out smart meters nationwide. Using smart meter data to infer building and heating system properties could, therefore, both contribute to the decarbonisation of the residential heating sector as well as providing a novel opportunity for the valorisation of smart-meter data. Computation models of buildings and heating systems may reproduce the dynamic behaviour of a building reliably. However, these methods often require detailed information about the building and its usage profile [2,3]. Either information is often unknown: building owners often do not have the expertise to determine this information, whereas energy consultants do not have access to the required information. In particular, if different retrofit options shall be compared to pick the optimal alternative, often only reference values are disposable [4–6]. On the other hand, smart grids measure the power consumption of the building as well as major appliances periodically in time steps from seconds

to minutes. If heat pumps are considered, these power consumption time series may provide substantial information about the dynamics of the building and its connected heating system. The methods used to automatically model the dynamics of the building and heating system and to reverse-engineer their properties from the power consumption time series can largely be divided into two fundamentally different approaches: The first family consists of the data-driven methods (black-box models), where generic fitting models (often with a high number of degrees of freedom and no explicit relation to building energy systems) are adapted to the available training data. Comprehensive literature reviews of data-driven models for energy demand prediction has been performed by Tardioli et al. [7] in 2015 and by Ahmad et al. in [8] in 2018. Typical examples include: dynamic system differential equation models [9], support vector regressions [10], regression models [11]. In [9], Gonzales et al. compared a black-box model (phenomenological differential equation) with simplified physical building models and showed that the black-box can outperform the physical model. For model families with a large number of parameters such as vector regression methods, it is vital that the adaption of model parameters can be performed automatically. Raetz et al. showed in [10] that automated modelling selection based on machine learning algorithms can outperform manual tuning of the models. Examples for these techniques are for instance regression methods and decision trees as studied by Ahmad et al. in [11]. Also for the prediction of energy demand

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Nomenclature

\dot{Q}_{ES}	Heat flux of emitter system [W]	$I(t)$	Solar radiation entering windows of building at time t [W]
$\dot{Q}_{internal}$	Heat flux of internal loads (appliances and inhabitants) [W]	T_{room}	Average room temperature in building model
$\dot{Q}_{measured}$	Heat consumption of real-world energy system at time slot t [J]	<i>Glossary</i>	
$\dot{Q}_{simulation}$	Heat consumption of energy system in simulation at time slot t [J]	IEA	International energy agency
C	Lumped capacity of the building [J/K]	L1	Integral norm
g	Solar contribution factor [-]	RMSE	Root mean square error
H	Lumped heat conductivity of the building [W/K]	SFH	Single Family Home

tree-based methods have been evaluated by Papadopoulos et al. in [12]. Eventually, also generic linear models from time series analysis like AR and MA or ARIMA and SARIMA have been investigated by Boroojeni et al. in [13] and Chujai [14], respectively. Also, in the field of artificial intelligence and deep learning the building energy demand estimation attracted substantial interest. In [15,16] artificial neural networks were tested and compared for building energy prediction. The work of Amber et al. in [17] presented artificial neural networks as the best alternative for daily building energy predictions, compared to support vector machines. In 2020, Ngarambe et al. [18] presented a review of current AI-based models for thermal control applications.

In the second family, the dynamics of the building and energy system is described by a physics-based simulation model (white-box models) and its parameters have to be adjusted to reproduce the actual power consumption profile best. A key difference of this type of approaches compared to the first family is that they often rely on the availability of a building or energy system layout and therefore, for each building a novel model and its parameters have to be identified. Simulation frameworks for building/energy system dynamics such as TRNSYS, EnergyPlus or IDA ICE [19,20] are in fact capable of predicting the building energy demands with high accuracy. Major drawback of white-box models is that only a small number of buildings can be modelled appropriately due to either the high computation demand [21], or due to the high amounts of detailed knowledge about the buildings necessary to model them correctly. Nevertheless, in [22] Nouvel et al. were able to create district-wide 3D models to estimate mean energy consumptions. In the field of district heating scenarios and demand response applications, Hedegaard et al. presented in [23] a bottom-up approach based on heat meter consumption data to model the individual buildings as well as to evaluate a simple price-driven demand-response scheme to reduce peak loads efficiently. In 2017, Lee et al. [24] inferred internal thermal masses by the analysis of data from smart thermostats. An impressive demonstration of the potential of using detailed white-box models (EnergyPlus) reverse engineer hard-to-measure building parameters based on detailed monitoring, is given in the works of Li et al. [25] and Hong et al. [26], where e.g. humidity or CO₂ concentration sensor data is evaluated in order to infer the amount of people in the building parts to increase simulation accuracy.

The overview above indicates that either detailed physics-based models or simple black-box models without physical interpretation of the extracted model parameters were investigated. Here, we would like to address this gap. This contribution presents a new method to characterise a building and its heating system as well as automatically generate a dynamic building and heating system model optimised for speed [4–6] based on smart meter consumption data of heat pumps only. This contribution extends preliminary results of a feasibility study applied to a single

building [27]. The anchor point of this approach is a simplified physical model of a residential building and its energy system implemented in a fast simulation framework [4–6]. The wide variety of different energy systems is condensed into a simple model with three free parameters. The key motivation of this step is to consider a simple model that should be flexible enough to capture the generic building dynamics and, therefore, can be applied on a wide variety of different buildings. Furthermore, this way, the number of required detailed information on the object can be reduced while the interpretation of the thermally relevant parameters remains possible. Additionally, the execution speed of the method offers the potential to investigate large areas up to nation scales and to provide information about the distribution of relevant building parameters and heating system in the respective areas. Considering the small retrofitting rate in the European Union, this approach offers a cost-efficient and easily deployable option to detect optimal candidates for retrofitting activities. With a relatively small computational time demand, the approach furthermore qualifies as a provider of short and long-term predictions of the heating demand for single residential buildings, multi-building areas up to district/city scale applications. These predictions enable, for instance, more accurate energy acquisition as well as virtual power plant applications, and thereby, can play an important role to enable a sustainable heating energy supply system. The validation and application presented here focussed on residential buildings. However, there are no intrinsic obstacles prohibiting a successful extension on commercial or industrial buildings.

This paper is organised as follows: In Section 2, the models and basic assumptions for the building model, the fitting procedure and the benchmark data and models are described. In Section 3, the results of the parameter estimation procedure both on reference models and real-world data are presented. In the last section, a conclusion about the applicability of the results is drawn.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Basic assumptions

The simulation algorithm relies on a simplified system model as presented in Fig. 1 [4–6]. The heat generated in the heat pump is transferred via pipes to the emitter system. The latter transmits heat to the building according to the radiator equation. The building dynamics is described by an established energy-balance model:

$$C \frac{\partial T_{room}}{\partial t} = -H(T_{room} - T_{ambient}) + gI + \dot{Q}_{Es} + \dot{Q}_{internal} \quad (1)$$

as introduced by Burmeister et al. [28]. This equation models the building as a single room with the temperature T_{room} and the capacity C . The temperature in the room changes upon the influx of solar

Fig. 1. Simulation model for the residential heating system composed of heat pump, emitter system and building. Details of the simulation model are presented in Section 2.3.

energy $g \cdot I(t)$ with the solar gain factor g and the solar radiation $I(t)$, the losses $H(T_{room} - T_{ambient})$ through the building surface, the heat contributions of inhabitants and appliances $\dot{Q}_{internal}$, and the heat introduced by the emitter system \dot{Q}_{ES} . Assuming default profiles for the contribution of inhabitants and appliances (extracted from [3] based on the regulations of the norm SIA 2024 from the Swiss Architects and Engineers [29]), three major parameters C, g and H must be defined to parameterise the system.

2.2. Algorithm for the building parameter determination

The procedure to determine the parameters C, g and H characterising the heating system and building slightly differs for the reference buildings and real-world buildings. In the reference case, where the actual values are already known, these values have been modified up to 30% to check if the optimization method still identifies the original values. This procedure serves as a basic validation of the method presented.

In the real-world case, initial values C_0, H_0 and g_0 have been estimated based on the results of the reference case. While C was set to its initial value, the initial values for g and H are taken as the centres of a grid, which contains 25 starting triplets. The grid should minimize the chance to end up in a local minimum during the optimization. For each point of this grid, the optimization procedure as described in Section 2.4 is performed. In a last step, the parameter C is optimized separately, where the optimum values found for g and H are kept constant.

2.3. Dynamic building and heating system simulation framework

The simulation of the building and residential heating system is implemented in the Retrosim framework [4–6]. In this framework, the building and heating system dynamics is simulated by solving coupled partial differential equations based on the energy and mass flow conservation. The configuration displayed in Fig. 1 is employed for the optimisation/parameter estimation process: The heat source (considered is a heat source with constant power) is connected via two pipes with the emitter system. The energy transferred to the building is calculated by the radiator equation employing a radiator factor of 1.3 to model a radiator based system. The heat transferred by the emitter system is considered as

the input \dot{Q}_{ES} for the building model detailed in Section 2.1 and Eq. (1). In the simulations performed in this context, only the parameters of the building C, H and g are adjusted. The heating system is operated by a two-point controller, which activates the heating system whenever the room temperature drops below 19.5 °C, and stops if the room temperature surpasses 20.5 °C.

2.4. Optimisation procedure

A Nelder-Mead algorithm is applied to optimise the cost function $L(C, H, g)$ and to determine the optimum parameters:

$$L(C, H, g) = \|Q_{measured} - Q_{simulation}(C, H, g)\|_2 \tag{2}$$

$$= \sqrt{\sum_{t \text{ time bin}} |Q_{measured}(t) - [Q_{simulation}(C, H, g)](t)|^2}$$

where $Q_{measured}(t)$ denotes the cumulated heat consumption until time bin t and $[Q_{simulation}(C, H, g)](t)$ the cumulated heat consumption as determined in the dynamic simulation with the parameters C, H, g until time bin t . The cumulative heat consumption has been chosen here to reduce the impact of short-term fluctuations of the heat consumption due to weather influences and user interactions. The optimisation of the parameters is implemented in python 3.6 employing the Nelder-Mead implementation from the scipy package 1.3.1. The entire process is visualized in Fig. 2.

2.5. Real-world benchmarking data

The benchmarking data for the five real-world systems are extracted from a monitoring study performed in the framework of the renewable heat premium payment scheme by the British Government [30–33]. A total of 700 buildings with heat pumps are monitored over individual periods of at least 13 months. As real-world application data, the method developed above is applied on five buildings from the above study. Only five buildings have been selected because these were the sole cases where the enthalpy fluxes to the space heating systems are measured synchronously besides the power consumption of the heat pump. Furthermore, the location of the buildings had to be identified. As the original data set only contained information about a reference year’s ambient temperature, the location, the actual ambient temperature and the solar radiation values are extracted from the

Fig. 2. Flow chart of proposed method to identify thermally relevant parameters.

Table 1

Comparison between the building/system properties for the reference buildings (column “Reference”) and the values extracted by the algorithm presented here (column “Algorithm”). Compared are the key properties describing the building dynamics as given in Eq. (1).

	Property	Algorithm	Reference	Fraction
SFH100	Capacity C (J/(K·m ²))	470089	436354	1.08
	Loss factor H (W/(K·m ²))	0.657	0.661	0.99
	Solar gain factor g	0.744	0.755	0.99
SFH45	Capacity C (J/(K·m ²))	328229	437380	0.75
	Loss factor H (W/(K·m ²))	0.287	0.284	1.01
	Solar gain factor g	0.642	0.622	1.03
SFH15	Capacity C (J/(K·m ²))	386642	437669	0.88
	Loss factor H (W/(K·m ²))	0.157	0.189	0.83
	Solar gain factor g	0.452	0.585	0.77

CEDA measurement station [34,35] with the most akin temperature profile (as determined by least squares’ method). As the values for the diffuse radiation are not provided in the above monitoring data, the values from the EnergyPlus weather data platform for London have been employed. Considered here are five single family houses with ground source heat pumps with ID 5145 (label A), ID 5150 (label B), ID 5237 (label C), ID 5344 (label D) and ID 5655 (label E). Buildings A, B and E are recent (built after 2000), buildings C and D are old buildings built before 1919. The modern buildings employ only underfloor heating as emitter, whereas the older buildings have partially also radiator systems. Building C has 3 bedrooms, the other buildings have four or more.

2.6. Validation procedures and reference building models

To assess the validity of the extracted building parameters, the procedure described above is applied on the heat consumption time series extracted from simulations of the three reference buildings: the single-family houses SFH15, SFH45 and SFH100 as defined in the IEA Annex Task 44 [3]. The key parameters of these buildings are reproduced in Table 1. The SFH100 is a model for a retrofitted old building with an annual space heating demand of 100 kWh/m². A typical modern building with an annual space heating energy demand of 45 kWh/m² is modelled with the SFH45 building type. Eventually, a low-energy certified building (according to the Minergie-P standard) is considered with the SFH15 model. Benchmark for the extraction procedure is how accurately the building properties are reproduced by the procedure described above (relative deviation).

In the real-world benchmark, the predicted heat consumption profile from the simulation and actual measurement data are employed because the actual building properties are not available. Numerically, two quantifiers are employed: First, the ratio of the area between the prediction and measured data curve and the area under the cumulated heat consumption. Second, the absolute deviation between the predicted annual heat consumption after one year and the actual consumption. Additionally, the root mean square error (RMSE) and the L1-norm for different aggregation periods have been calculated, normalized by the mean of the real-world consumption. For comparability, these numbers are also calculated for the SFH reference cases.

2.7. Assessment of algorithm stability

The proposed method relies on initial parameter values for the optimisation. To quantify the effect of the choice of initial values on the accuracy of the determined building properties, each starting value is varied over a range of plus and minus 30% and the optimisation is repeated for each parameter triple. For the reference buildings, the deviation of the optimised parameter set from the actual parameter set is analysed. To assess the stability of the

results for the real-world buildings, the effect of change of the individual parameters by 5% on the loss function is assessed for all five real-world buildings.

3. Results

3.1. Validation results with reference buildings

The reconstructed profiles of the heat consumption for the three reference buildings SFH15, SFH45 and SFH100 are displayed in Fig. 3. For the buildings SFH45 and SFH100, the reference simulation results and the results of the procedure presented here match almost perfectly and the two profiles are indiscernible in the considered resolution. For the low-energy consumption building SFH15, slight deviations at the verge and the rise of the heating season can be noted. The results of the parameter estimation study

Fig. 3. Cumulative heat consumption of the considered three reference buildings SFH15, SFH45 and SFH100. Compared are the cumulated space heating energy demand for reference simulations and the simulation performed with the recovered parameter values (cf. Table 1).

Table 2

Numerical quantifiers of the deviation between simulated and actual heat consumption for the real-world benchmark as well as the simulation reference buildings. Displayed is the ration "Area ratio" of the area between simulated and actual heat consumption and area under the reference heat consumption, as well as the relative deviation of total annual heat consumption (column "relative change").

Building	Area ratio [%]	Relative change [%]
A	2.4	8.9
B	1.5	4.0
C	1.7	4.2
D	1.5	-0.5
E	4.2	-2.0
SFH15	1.09	-1.44
SFH45	0.27	0.00
SFH100	0.04	0.02

for the three buildings are reproduced in Table 1. The loss factor H and the solar gain factor g are very well reproduced for SFH45 and SFH100. On the other hand, the estimated capacity of the building deviates more strongly from the reference values. This mismatch is explained by the sensitivity analysis displayed in Section 3.4. On the other hand, the parameters of the low-energy consumption building are underestimated by 10–20%. An explanation for this systematic discrepancy could be that the SFH15 model considers an exhaust air heat recovery system, which is not considered in the simulation model for the parameter estimation process. The exhaust air heat recovery system is not considered as a feature of the physical model because it is not a wide-spread feature in the whole building park. To assess the quality of the obtained results numerically in terms of heat consumption, the ratio between the area between simulated and reference heat consumptions and the area of the reference heat consumption, as well as the relative deviation in the total annual heat consumption is considered (cf. Table 2).

3.2. Stability of estimation procedure for reference buildings

Fig. 4 shows how the optimization procedure is affected by a significant change of the initial parameter values. For the buildings SFH45 and SFH100, 4 of 8 starting triplets yield after optimisation a building parameter set lying within a 5% border around the actual values. For the remaining cases the optimisation yields parameter values leaving the 5% deviation regime only marginally. For SFH15, the optimal values identified deviate slightly more, as expected, considering the missing exhaust air heat exchange. However, this result confirms the validity of the used grid approach and enables an upper boundary estimation for the step size of the grid in the optimization procedure.

3.3. Application to real-world buildings

To check the applicability of the presented procedure on real-world buildings, data from five buildings in Great Britain as monitored within the framework of the RHPP of the British Government are considered (cf. Section 2.5 for details). The results of the procedure described in Section 2.2 is shown in Figs. 5 and 6.

Fig. 5 displays the results for building 5344. For this building, the heat consumption simulated with the recovered parameters and the actual heat consumption are almost indiscernible. Furthermore, the total heat consumptions match up to 1% after a full year. Only in the beginning of summer, a slightly higher heat consumption in the simulated profile is noticeable. The application of the presented method on four further buildings displayed in Fig. 6 confirmed the excellent agreement observed for building D. Remarkably, for all five buildings, the accurate estimation of the seasonal

transition periods plays a key role for the accuracy of the prediction.

Fig. 4. Stability analysis of parameter estimation for reference buildings SFH15, SFH45 and SFH100. Depicted are the optimal values found (dots) for H for different starting values. The crosses in the inset plot and their colours refer to the different initial values tested for the parameters g and C . The dashed lines are located at 5% deviation to the actual value (solid grey line).

Fig. 5. Comparison of heat consumption profiles for building 5344 (D). The simulations based on the parameters C , g and H reproduce the heat consumption profiles of real-world monitoring data (in black) very accurately.

Fig. 6. Comparison of heat consumption profiles as extracted from the real-world measurements in black and the simulations with the parameters determined by the presented procedure in red. Examples are shown for building label A (top), building label B (center top), building label C (center bottom) and building label E (bottom). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

To assess the quality of real-world application numerically, the ratio between the area between simulated and reference heat consumptions and the area of the reference heat consumption, as well as the relative deviation in the total annual heat consumption is

considered (cf. Table 2). To justify the comparison of the results between SFH reference and real-world case, these values have also been calculated for the SFH reference case.

In Figs. 7 and 8, a comparison of reproduced and actual heat consumption for different aggregation periods is shown for buildings E and SFH45, respectively. Building E has been chosen as a problematic example for the real-world situation and it is compared to SFH45 because of the similarity in total heat consumption. In the SFH case, only slight deviations in each sub-plot are noticeable as expected. For building E, there is a good match for the monthly and weekly aggregation period. However, in the transition period from spring to summer the heat consumption is slightly overestimated, whereas in the transition period from summer to autumn the consumption is underestimated. An explanation could be stronger deviations between the weather conditions in simulations and the actual weather situation during the data recording. The daily aggregation plot shows big differences between the

Fig. 7. Comparison of heat consumption profiles for different aggregation periods for building E of the real-world benchmarking data set. Compared are the actual reference consumption (black dashed line with label “Ref”) and the profiles from the simulation with the extracted parameters (red solid line with label “Rec”).

Fig. 8. Comparison of heat consumption profiles for different aggregation periods for SFH45. Compared are the actual reference consumption (black dashed line with label “Ref”) and the profiles from the simulation with the extracted parameters (red solid line with label “Rec”). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

simulation result and the real data and is discussed more detailed in the next paragraph. To assess the quality of the obtained results, the ratio between the L1-norm of the difference of the heat simulated and reference heat consumptions and the area of the reference heat consumption, as well as the relative deviation in total annual heat consumption is provided in Table 2. To compare the results from the SFH reference with the real-world case, these values have also been calculated for the SFH reference case.

For the daily aggregated data, the two profiles mismatch stronger. However, an oscillatory behaviour of the simulated profile around the actual profile can be observed. These deviations might be a consequence of the chosen heating system controller. The simulation model employs a simple two-point controller, whereas real-world heat pumps often include a smoothing PID style controller causing a smoother system behaviour. This explanation is supported by a more detailed comparison (zoomed version of daily aggregated plots in Figs. 7 and 8 for the period from November 28th till December 21st) of the daily aggregation periods provided

Fig. 9. Comparison of heat consumption profiles between 28th November 2014 and 21st December 2014 for building E. The results of the simulation with the recovered parameters are shown in red, the reference simulation is shown in black. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 10. Comparison of heat consumption profiles between 28th November 2014 and 21st December 2014 for the simulation reference building SFH45. The results of the simulation with the recovered parameters are shown in red, the reference simulation is shown in black. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

in Figs. 9 and 10. A period of excessive heating in the simulation is followed by a period without heating to compensate for the heat surplus produced before. Another possible explanation could be an overestimation of the building's capacity C , leading to an increased reaction time of the system upon the activation of the heating system.

A numerical comparison of the quantifiers for the deviations of the respective aggregation periods is shown in Table 3, where the RMSE and L1-norm of the difference of the profiles, both normalized by the reference aggregation mean, are shown for each building. For the real-world buildings the values vary only mildly among different buildings for the same level of aggregation. For comparisons among different aggregation periods one has to consider the smoothening effects of the aggregation on the norm calculation as well as on the mean value. For example, if the deviations of simulation data and real data are modelled by a Gaussian distribution and we compare it to an aggregated version with period p , an increase of L1/mean by a factor $\sqrt{p} * p$ is implicit.

Table 3

Evaluation of performance: comparison of root mean square error (RMSE) and L1-norm of the difference between simulated and actual heat consumption profile, both normalized with respect to the corresponding mean consumption of the aggregation periods. Considered are the five real-world benchmarking buildings as well as three simulation reference buildings.

Metric	Building	Monthly	Weekly	Daily	
L1/mean	A	2.08	11.25	215.08	
	B	1.2	9.85	208.77	
	C	1.35	9.14	179.9	
	D	1.45	11.14	217.37	
	E	2.2	16.38	382.37	
	SFH100	0.02	0.46	5.47	
	SFH45	0.26	3.18	142.49	
	SFH15	1.02	7.16	260.08	
	RMSE/mean	A	0.97	2.35	19.24
		B	0.54	1.86	16.56
C		0.52	1.67	13.14	
D		0.5	2.34	16.07	
E		0.81	3.13	29.72	
SFH100		0.01	0.16	1.27	
SFH45		0.11	0.78	17.64	
SFH15		0.46	1.85	33.49	

Fig. 11. Sensitivity analysis of the three considered parameters C , H and g for the five considered real-world buildings on the cost function. Displayed is its increase after an addition/subtraction of 5% to the actual parameter value.

3.4. Sensitivity analysis of optimization loss function for real-world buildings

As depicted in Fig. 11, the sensitivity analysis displays a strong dependence of the optimization cost function on the loss parameter H and the solar gain factor g . The capacity has almost no effect. In conclusion, the estimation of the building capacity is a very challenging task because strong variations in the capacity yield only minor differences in the cost function. This dependence explains the separate treatment of this parameter in the optimization procedure.

4. Conclusions

In this contribution, a new method for the characterisation of buildings and heating system based on smart meter data from heat pumps is introduced. The achieved results for the prediction of the heat consumption profile as well as the recovered building/heating system properties clearly indicated that the proposed procedure with a fast simulation tool is able to recover the targeted parameters and profiles. For simulation reference cases, the annual heat consumption could be reproduced by up to 1.5%. Heat loss H and solar gain g factors of the reference cases were recovered with an accuracy higher than 97% in two cases (SFH100 and SFH45) and the slightly larger deviations in the third (SFH15) case. The deviation for SFH15 presumably is rooted in a system configuration mismatch. These results indicate that the larger the actual total heat consumption of the buildings is (SFH X is a single-family house with X kWh/m²/a annual space heating demand) the easier it is to recover the actual building parameters. A putative explanation for this behaviour is the much bigger effect of user interactions in buildings with a low total heat consumption. The application of the novel algorithm on real-world examples lead to excellent reproductions of the annual space heating demands. The deviation of the total annual space heating demand is less than 5% in 4 of 5 cases. Also if shorter aggregation periods are chosen (weekly, monthly) a good agreement is found. However, the mismatch strongly increases if the heat consumption is aggregated daily. Putative reason for this mismatch is a different control strategy in the simulations compared to the actual controllers. The sensitivity analysis of the procedure on the choice of the initial parameters revealed that the buildings capacity is the parameter hardest to recover with the proposed method. However, even with a change of 25%, the heat consumption could be excellently reproduced and only for correct short-term predictions a precise recovery of the capacity is required.

The current limitations of the procedure become visible in the daily aggregated estimation of the building's heat consumption and are mainly caused by the following three reasons. First, the weather conditions, in particular local solar irradiation, can always only be roughly estimated in the proposed method when using weather station data. Shading of trees or (high) neighbouring buildings may cause a more substantial deviation from meteorological data than the switch to a neighbouring weather station. Another important point is the control algorithm of the heat pump. For consumption profiles on a daily and higher resolution, tiny deviations of parameters (e.g. on-set parameters) can cause a substantial deviation of the demand profile. To overcome such shortcomings and still be able to predict energy consumption on hourly time scales for single buildings, future work needs to address the problem of inferring control parameters and try to adopt them directly. Furthermore, the procedure so far has only been tested on residential buildings modelled as a single unit. Effects stemming from different geometry, therefore, have not been considered.

Nevertheless, these results recommend the approach as a potential demand prediction tool, which has various possible use cases. As a first example, a notification application is under development, where the actual heating behaviour is constantly compared against the expected ranges, to detect e.g. sudden, unexpected increases in energy consumption. As a second example, a model-based representation of the heating system can serve as a digital twin representation and support predictive maintenance applications. Slowly developing discrepancies of a system can be more accurately detected if the system's performance is compared to a second (virtual) system. In future work, the applicability for hour to hour predictions will be investigated. A major challenge will be the sources for the discrepancies in the daily aggregation described above. Furthermore, the results in this study qualify the proposed method to be usable for a large-scale study and district prediction applications. As a third example, if the consumption of entire networks has to be predicted, small deviations of single buildings cancel out each other for a sufficiently large network. Even various individual controlling schemes will add up to a mixed district controlling scheme, which further mitigates some of the limitations experienced in the current study. As an explicit realization of a large-scale study exploiting the promising results of the building parameter extraction, based on the proposed method, a classification algorithm for residential buildings identifying potential renovation candidates is achievable.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

P. Schuetz: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing - original draft, Supervision. **A. Melillo:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing - original draft. **F. Businger:** Investigation, Methodology. **R. Durrer:** Data curation. **S. Frehner:** Data curation. **D. Gwerder:** Resources. **J. Worlitschek:** Project administration.

Declaration of Competing Interest

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